

Research Article

Green Fashion Recycled Application

Nurhidayah Rosely^{1,*}, Ayu Kamareenna Abdullah Thani², Siti Rosnita Sakarji³, and An Nur Nabila Ismail⁴

¹ Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Kelantan; nurhidayahrosely@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0001-9367-6998

² Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Kelantan; ayukamareenna@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0001-7851-2354

³ Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Kelantan, rosnita507@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-1281-2167

⁴ Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Kelantan, annurnabila@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0001-5790-1983

* Correspondence: nurhidayahrosely@uitm.edu.my; 0126159531.

Abstract: *The emergence of the fast fashion market could be attributed as a cause of the environment destruction as consumers' spending patterns have been changed due to the overproduction, reducing the price of the fashion goods. As fashion has a short life-cycle and trends quickly fade, consumers find there is a need to keep purchasing the latest trend instead of wearing the fashion goods for a long-term, causing them to discard the outdated collection. Among the issues of this fast-fashion market is how consumers dispose and discard the unwanted fashion goods in a sustainable way. To date, communities or individuals need to bring and come to the assigned recycling centers or find the recycling box to discard their unwanted fashion items which is sometimes not accessible and time-consuming for the community to practice the recycling activities. Consequently, most of the community choose to dump their unwanted fashion item into the garbage or trash bin, then thrown into dumpsites, causing severe overflowing landfills across Malaysia. Therefore, this business idea would like to address fashion goods disposal issues among Malaysian society, and encourage the community to practice sustainable lifestyle through fashion goods recycling application. This application enables the community to find the nearest recycling centers with the collector or pick-up services with some charges. The target market of this application is a community that loves to shop and purchase fashion goods such as apparels, hijab and scarves, bags and shoes, which are willing to pay for the services and would like to practice sustainable lifestyles.*

Keywords: recycled application; fashion goods; sustainable lifestyles.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888367

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of overproduction and overconsumption becomes a barrier for Malaysia to achieve SDG 12, as both manufacturers and consumers are not concerned with their actions, as they only care to satisfy their material needs and wants. Factors such as an inexpensive price motivate consumers to keep purchasing and consuming the latest design and collection of fashion goods, and consumers are able to replenish their wardrobe instead of thinking about how to discard or dispose of the existing fashion goods without creating a harmful effect on the environment. According to Kloth Cares, the first textile recycling movement in Southeast Asia, Malaysia dumped a staggering 195,300 metric tonnes of fabric into landfills, and the amount of textile waste that ends up in landfills has doubled from 2.8% in 2012 to 6.3%, contributed by the development of the fast-fashion industry (Malay Mail, 2019). They also reveal that the youth are a major market segment for fast fashion, and the fashion industry itself is the second largest polluter after oil and gas. Apparently, consumers themselves are

not aware of how their overconsumption practices contribute to the major destruction of the environment and also to an individual's wellbeing.

In a different vein, The National Sustainable Consumption and Production Blueprint, 2016–2030, outlines one of the mechanisms towards developing a circular economy waste system: consumers, which have been defined as waste holders, should be responsible and join hands with the waste generator, the manufacturer, to phase out conventional landfilling by 2030 (The National SCP Blueprint 2016–2030, (2016). Hence, it is expected that consumers will keep discarding their clothes, and more than 150 million metric tonnes of fashion waste will clog landfills by 2050 (The Malaysian Reserve, 2022). Therefore, consumers themselves need to change their attitudes, consumption, and disposal patterns to save the environment instead of relying on the initiative taken by the government or a non-governmental organisation. To date, a lot of initiatives and campaigns have been implemented, such as the bin adoption program, recycling and upcycling clothes, and turning waste into other products, but they are still not enough to solve this environmental problem.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Fast fashion consumers purchase 60 percent more clothes compared to 20 years ago, and the consumption only lasts less than one year, meaning over 50% of the clothes end up in landfills. The issue and problem faced by the consumers/individuals to recycle their unwanted fashion goods are to bring and find the nearest recycle center that causes them to dump the textile waste into their dustbin and end up in a garbage truck.

3. FINDINGS

Due to the time factor and inconveniences, there is a need to develop an application for the community to encourage and promote sustainable consumption practices. Previously, the recycling campaign has been done by the government and non-government organization to educate and create awareness among Malaysian people to protect the environment. However, studies found that the existing campaign, ineffective due to the convenience, practicality and accessibility factors.

Thus, developing fashion goods or apparel applications might be successful to promote sustainable lifestyle among Malaysian people. This platform helps consumers to identify the nearest location/ recycle box to dispose of their unwanted fashion goods using Location-based Service. Besides Administrator that manage the application, there are three types of users in this system:

- Individual/client who would like to discard their fashion goods items (recycle)
- The collector/runner that will pick up/collect the recycled items
- The recycle center

Figure 1. Green Fashion Recycled Application Process

4. DISCUSSION

This business idea is proposed with the aim to build a mobile application in order to promote and encourage sustainable lifestyles through recycling fashion goods among the Malaysian community. The application is going to help the community, specifically fashion consumers to discard their unwanted fashion goods in a sustainable way, besides providing job opportunities to the communities such as the delivery runner or collectors. Furthermore, the recycling center could collaborate with the fashion industries and non-government organization for the upcycling project of the unwanted collection of fashion goods. The user that would like to recycle their items, might categorise the condition of the fashion items such as excellent, good, poor to enable the recycle centers sorting the fashion goods for the further process of donation. The application also provides information on the nearest recycled center of the users' location and once the request has been made, the application will search the nearby collectors to collect and deliver the boxes or package of fashion goods. Users or clients need to fill up the details such as sizes, quantity, weight of package or boxes to allow the application to determine the rate and charges of the services.

Overall, the idea is targeting users that are willing to pay for the services to discard and dispose of their unwanted fashion items that are no longer relevant for them to be kept and stored. To date, Kloth Cares, a social enterprise has placed over 80 bins across Klang Valley to encourage the public to dispose of their unwanted fabric and clothes, which might be one of the best initiatives from the organization to foster and educate the community in practicing sustainable lifestyle (Malay Mail, 2019).

Popular brands and organization such as UNIQLO, H&M and Tudung FAZURA, provide some incentives and rewards to their customers to support the recycle program, but still require customers to come and bring their unwanted apparel to their boutique. Therefore, to promote the sustainability of those recycle program which have been implemented by various organization, there is a need to introduce a convenient and practical platform such as application, to encourage the community to participate in this recycle program.

5. CONCLUSION

The idea to develop recycling applications for fashion goods is still under-explored as the existing recycling application does not cover fashion items. Currently, the fashion industry encourages the community to walk-in and bring all their unwanted fashion items, which is not convenient and time consuming. In response to promote sustainable lifestyle and protect the environment, this proposed application aims to inspire and motivate communities to practice sustainable lifestyles through their consumption practice. Hence, this application also hopes to contribute job opportunities to the community and enhance creativity and innovativeness to upcycling the unwanted fashion items instead of discarding them into the landfill.

References

- Malay Mail (2019). Those old clothes you have? Don't dump it, recycle it.
<https://www.malaymail.com/news/life/2019/02/25/those-old-clothes-you-have-dont-dump-it-recycle-it/1726674>
- The Malaysian Reserve (2022). The Big Waste – one artist mission to reduce fashion waste.
<https://themalaysianreserve.com/2022/05/05/the-big-waste-one-artist-mission-to-reduce-fashion-waste/>
- THE NATIONAL SCP BLUEPRINT. The Pathways for Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP) in Malaysia 2016-2030 (2016).
https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/malaysia_the_national_scp_blueprint_2016_-_2030.pdf